

The Biochemistry of Skin Pigmentation and its Relation to Melanoma

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The biochemistry of melanogenesis has been under investigation for more than 100 years. In the mouse, some 130 coat colour mutations exist at more than 50 genetic loci. This vast array of genes, many of them interacting with one another, attests both to the evolutionary importance of the pigmentary system as well as to the difficulties encountered in unravelling the underlying biochemical processes. In addition, the pigmentary system, which provides protection from solar radiation, is ironically the same system from which melanomas are generated. This article, dedicated to Professor D. P. Chakraborty, summarises some of the progress from our laboratory in this complex and fascinating field of research.

The pigmentary system of the skin has evolved, at least in part, to provide protection against the damaging effects of solar radiation. Epidemiological data indicate an inverse relationship between skin melanin content and sun-induced skin damage, including melanoma and other cancers of the skin. Melanins are biopolymers composed of indoles and indolequinones, such as 5,6-dihydroxyindole and 5,6-dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid. Understanding how these precursors become incorporated into melanin requires research efforts at many levels—including the expression of specialised genes regulating the pigmentary system, the enzymatic conversion of tyrosine and dihydroxyphenylalanine into indoles, the sub-cellular organisational apparatus for synthesising and compartmentalising melanins, the autocrine and paracrine production of hormones, regulation of hormone receptors, cell-cell interactions, and the conversion of electromagnetic energy from ultraviolet radiation into appropriate biochemical signals to initiate the process of melanisation. Furthermore, the mechanisms by which normal melanocytes become transformed into primary and metastatic melanomas may be intimately linked to the above processes.

The purpose of this article is to review work from our laboratory related to the above

processes. We are pleased to dedicate this article to Professor D. P. Chakraborty, whose curiosity and enthusiasm for understanding the basic chemistry of these problems has inspired our laboratory from the other side of the world.

Enzymatic control of melanisation

The biosynthesis of melanin is observed by anyone who leaves the surface of a cut apple, potato or banana exposed to air¹. The first biochemical investigations were performed on the mushroom *Russula nigricans*, whose cut flesh turns red and then black on exposure to air². The mushrooms were boiled in ethanol and a colourless substrate was extracted which reacted with the 'oxidising ferment' of the mushrooms to yield first a red and then a black compound. The colourless substrate was tyrosine, the oxidising ferment was mushroom tyrosinase, and the red and black compounds were dopachrome and melanin, respectively.

Over the next 30 years, tyrosinase was demonstrated in insects and vertebrates and used to elucidate further intermediates in the pathway of melanin biosynthesis. However, it is important to note that many of the earlier experiments utilised crude preparations of mushroom tyrosinase

as the catalytic source. These studies formed the basis for the classic 'Mason-Raper Pathway' which remains today our principal metabolic scheme for conceptualising eumelanogenesis. In this linear scheme, dopachrome loses its carboxyl group to form 5,6-dihydroxyindole (DHI). DHI is oxidised to indole-5,6-quinone and then to melanochrome, a purple compound which polymerises to melanin.

It is interesting that most of the previously published 'Mason-Raper' schemes did not even include the structure of 5,6-dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid (DHICA), but showed instead the release of CO₂ following the decarboxylation of dopachrome. Results from these earlier studies, particularly those employing mushroom tyrosinase, indicated that DHICA was either non-existent or a very short-lived structure. Indeed, our laboratory has found that DHICA is rapidly decarboxylated to DHI by extracts of mushrooms, and a black, insoluble melanin precipitate is formed.

However, direct analyses of melanins from various zoological sources have shown that they contain unexpectedly high contents of carboxyl groups, inconsistent with predictions from studies with mushroom tyrosinase³⁻⁷. The carboxyl groups are apparently derived from the incorporation of DHICA monomers into melanin⁶.

One explanation for the occurrence of DHICA monomers in natural melanins comes from the findings of the past decade that mammalian melanocytes can convert dopachrome to DHICA (see below). Another explanation comes from the observations that at physiological pH and temperature, DHICA is stable and does not readily lose its carboxyl group to form DHI⁸⁻¹⁰. Thus DHICA, once thought at best to be only a transitory intermediate, appears to be a major factor in mammalian melanin biosynthesis¹¹. Therefore, for the Mason-Raper Pathway to be representative of mammalian melanogenesis, there should be at least one branch point at the conversion of dopachrome to either DHI or DHICA (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the mammalian melanogenesis pathway as it is currently envisioned. The scheme differs from the original pathway of Mason and Raper in that DHICA (5,6-dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid) is enzymatically produced from dopachrome via the enzyme dopachrome tautomerase (E.C. 5.3.2.3, shown here as dopachrome isomerase). Also shown are as yet hypothetical activities that convert DHICA into melanin (DHICA Conversion Factor) and/or stabilise DHICA from oxidative polymerisation (Stablin). It may be noted that tyrosinase has been shown, at least *in vitro*, to function at three points in the pathway. Arrows denote points thought to be regulated by MSH.

Dopachrome, an intermediate in melanin biosynthesis, exhibits some unusual properties. At physiologic pH (e.g. pH 6–8) it is unstable and spontaneously loses its carboxyl group to form 5,6-dihydroxyindole (DHI) and CO₂. However, over this same pH range, if various metals or a melanocyte-specific enzyme are present, it rapidly rearranges to its isomer form – DHICA – which is far more stable than dopachrome in its ability to retain the carboxyl group. Whether or not the carboxyl group is retained could have important implications for the regulation of melanogenesis, since in the presence of oxygen DHI spontaneously forms a black precipitate, whereas DHICA forms a golden-brown solution. The solubility of ‘DHICA-melanin’ is due to the presence of carboxyl groups which provide negative charges and hydrophilicity. Thus, *in vivo*, the extent to which dopachrome is converted to DHI or DHICA may well influence the solubility and colour of the melanin formed¹².

Dopachrome tautomerase (DT) is a melanocyte-specific, membrane-associated, heat-labile, non-dialysable, protease-sensitive factor which catalyses the isomeric rearrangement of dopachrome to 5,6-dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid (DHICA), apparently through a tautomerisation reaction. Metal ions such as Cu, Ni, Co, Zn, Mn, Ca, Al and Fe can also catalyse the dopachrome/ DHICA isomerisation. How is the reaction regulated *in vivo*? An attractive possibility would be that DT is a metalloenzyme. Indeed, we have obtained evidence that this may indeed be the case¹³. Purified preparations of DT and tyrosinase, obtained from Cloudman S91 mouse melanoma cells, were assayed in the presence of a variety of metal chelators including EDTA (predominantly Ca and Mg), EGTA (predominantly Ca), phenylthiourea (PTU) (predominantly Cu), 2,2'-dipyridyl (predominantly Fe), 1,10-phenanthroline (predominantly Fe) and 2,3-dihydroxybenzoic acid (predominantly Fe). Results were as follows : (i) iron chelators inhibited DT activity with no effects on tyrosinase activity, (ii) PTU inhibited

tyrosinase activity with no effects on DT activity and (iii) the Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ chelators had little effect on either enzymatic activity. In addition, studies with glycosylation inhibitors, glycosylase enzymes and immobilised lectins indicated that DT is a glycoprotein. The results suggest that DT is a metal-containing glycosylated enzyme, possibly with ferrous iron at its catalytic center.

DT is therefore an enzymatic activity associated with the pigmentary system which catalyses the conversion of dopachrome, an intermediate in melanin biosynthesis to DHICA. To date, the mechanism of action of DT has been unknown because all previous assays have employed a dopachrome substrate contaminated with L-dopa. It has therefore not been possible to determine whether L-dopa acts as a hydrogen donor in the reaction or whether the formation of DHICA occurs through an isomerisation of dopachrome. We demonstrated that DT catalyses the conversion of dopachrome to DHICA equally well in the presence or absence of L-dopa. The DT-mediated reaction thus appears to be an isomeric rearrangement of hydrogen ions from one portion of the dopachrome molecule to another.

Hormonal control of melanisation : a potential interface with uv radiation

Exposure of skin to sunlight or selected wavelengths of ultraviolet (uv) radiation provides a positive signal to the pigmentary system. This results in an increase in the number of active melanocytes as well as an increase in the rate of melanin synthesis within individual melanocytes. The dendritic transfer of melanin from melanocytes to surrounding keratinocytes may also be enhanced^{14–17}.

It is ironic that the cutaneous pigmentary system, which protects skin from solar radiation, is also the system from which melanomas are generated. Epidemiologic studies agree that the incidences of malignant melanoma and other forms of skin cancer are increasing in humans, and

there is considerable evidence that uv light is a major causative factor¹⁸⁻²¹. Understanding the normal processes by which uv light stimulates melanogenesis should provide important information as to how melanomas arise.

Elder²² has reviewed the literature on the possible association between solar radiation and melanoma. He concludes the following : (a) there is increased risk of melanoma in fair-skinned races and, in general, the risk increases the closer an individual lives to the equator, (b) anatomical site distribution studies in general (but not always) point to sun-exposed areas of skin as being at increased risk for melanoma, (c) there is a positive correlation between frequency of sun exposure (burning episodes in particular) and the incidence of melanoma, (d) there is a positive correlation between actinic skin damage and the incidence of melanoma, (e) dysplastic nevi, potential precursors of melanoma, are generally more abundant in sun exposed areas and (f) individuals with the genetic disorder xeroderma pigmentosum have a 2000-fold greater risk of developing melanoma than those in the normal human population²³. Xeroderma pigmentosum is characterised by a decreased ability to repair damaged DNA, and is manifest by an extreme sensitivity to the effects of solar radiation.

From these observations, it seems reasonable to conclude that solar radiation is a causative factor in melanoma. However, we do not yet understand the mechanisms by which the uv-induced transformation of melanocytes to melanoma cells occurs.

At least two pathways for the induction of melanomas by uv light are possible. These are diagrammed as a hypothesis in Fig. 2 and have been discussed by Elder²². The first pathway would involve genetic damage and mutagenic change that results in malignant transformation, e.g. through the activation of an oncogene. Since it is well known that mutagens are carcinogenic²⁴ and that uv light is a mutagen²⁵, it seems

likely that at least some of the sun-related skin cancers occur through mutagenesis. Indeed, recent evidence has linked exposure of humans to solar radiation with mutations in the p53 protein and the development of cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma²⁶. A second proposed pathway for uv-induced melanoma is one unique to the biology of the pigmentary system (Fig. 2). That is, one of the early responses of the pigmentary

Fig. 2 Two hypothetical pathways for the generation of melanomas and other skin cancers by ultraviolet radiation. The left-hand pathway represents a mutational activation of oncogenes, whereas the right-hand pathway represents situations in which melanomas are generated when the normal regulatory processes of melanogenesis are in some manner disturbed, including mutationally. Pathways 1 and 2 are not mutually exclusive. The hypothesis encompasses the onset of primary, immortalised melanomas, and does not necessarily include the generation of metastatic melanomas.

system to uv light is to increase the number of active melanocytes in the skin. This occurs apparently through a stimulus for otherwise quiescent cells to re-enter the cell cycle^{15,16}. Perhaps during this process melanocytes occasionally lose their ability to turn off the mitogenic signal, and as such become permanently transformed into melanoma cells.

Pathways 1 and 2 (Fig. 2) are not mutually exclusive and both could easily be playing a role. For example, a mutagenic event could activate an oncogene (pathway 1) which then results in a loss of the mitogenic 'off' signal

(pathway 2). In both cases, uv-induced immunosuppression could allow for the newly-transformed melanoma cell to proliferate with reduced opposition from the immune system²⁷.

Thus, exposure of the skin to uv light results in a molecular cascade which ultimately increases the melanin content of keratinocytes. It is possible that these highly complex process may occasionally go awry, resulting in malignant transformation of cells. Understanding the various steps in the cascade should help reveal which pathways might be involved in the transformation process.

Ultraviolet B radiation (UVB) elicits an increase in melanin production in mammalian skin. The mechanisms regulating this process are not understood, although it is well documented that there is an increase in the number of melanin-producing melanocytes. The melanotropins (MSH) are a family of peptides that increase the melanin content of melanocytes through an interaction with high affinity receptors. We have obtained evidence that the effects of UVB on melanogenesis may be mediated through an increase in MSH receptor activity on melanocytes. First, exposure of Cloudman S91 mouse melanoma cells to UVB resulted in increased binding of ¹²⁵I-MSH to cells within 24 h²⁸. In five separate experiments, UVB-irradiated cultures displayed 2-10-fold increases in MSH binding capacity over that of unirradiated control cultures (optimum doses 10–20 mJ cm⁻²). Second, UVB and MSH potentiated one another in promoting cutaneous melanogenesis in both mice and guinea pigs. In the areas of guinea pig skin that received both UVB and MSH, there was a five-fold increase in active melanocytes/mm² over the sum of active melanocytes/mm² in areas receiving either MSH or UVB separately. Our results suggest that UVB light causes an increase in MSH receptor activity on cutaneous melanocytes, thus increasing cellular responsiveness to MSH. Implicit in this mechanism is a transduction of radiant energy into chemical energy during the process of UVB-induced melanogenesis.

Expression of internal receptors for MSH is an important criterion for responsiveness to MSH by Cloudman melanoma cells²⁹. We have shown that internal and external receptors for MSH are of identical molecular weights (50–53 kDa) and share common antigenic determinants, indicating a structural relationship between the two populations of molecules. The internal receptors co-purified with a sub-cellular fraction highly enriched for small vesicles, many of which were coated. Ultraviolet B light (UVB) acted synergistically with MSH to increase tyrosinase activity and melanin content of cultured Cloudman melanoma cells, consistent with previous findings in the skin of mice and guinea pigs²⁸. Preceding the rise in tyrosinase activity in cultured cells, UVB elicited a decrease in internal MSH binding sites and a concomittant increase in external sites. The time-frame for the UVB effects on MSH receptors and melanogenesis, 48 h, was similar to that for a response to solar radiation in humans. Together, the results indicate a key role for MSH receptors in the induction of melanogenesis by UVB and suggest a potential mechanism of action for UVB : redistribution of MSH receptors with a resultant increase in cellular responsiveness to MSH.

MSH can up-regulate MSH binding capacity of cultured Cloudman melanoma cells in a dose- and time-dependent fashion³⁰. Binding is mediated through proteins exhibiting an apparent molecular weight of 50–53 kDa, consistent with previous studies implicating them as the principal MSH receptors on Cloudman cells. Pre-incubation of cells with MSH stimulates expression of the receptor proteins both on the plasma membrane surface as well as in internal sites associated with coated vesicles. The effects of MSH are additive with those of uv light, suggesting that uv and MSH might stimulate receptor expression through separate mechanisms.

Receptors for melanotropin (MSH) were found to be expressed by immortalised primary human

epidermal keratinocytes (RHEK-1)³¹. Using ¹²⁵I- β MSH as a probe, the MSH receptors from mouse melanoma cells and human keratinocytes were found to be remarkably similar. In each cell line, there were high and low affinity receptors, with the high affinity classes showing positive cooperativity. Competition of ¹²⁵I- β MSH for binding with non-radioactive MSH revealed similar profiles. Cross-linking studies, followed by gel electrophoresis and autoradiography showed almost identical gel migration patterns. Both cell types expressed internal as well as plasma membrane binding sites. MSH receptors on both cell types were up-regulated by ultraviolet light, and by MSH itself. Although the function of MSH receptors expressed by the immortalised keratinocytes is unknown, the results are consistent with recent reports that proliferation of epidermal keratinocytes is stimulated by MSH and that proopiomelanocortin genes are expressed in the epidermis. These results support a model in which keratinocytes and melanocytes, interacting in an 'epidermal melanin unit' each respond to uv light signals with increased MSH receptor activity.

Conclusion :

The pigmentary system functions through complex interactions between ultraviolet radiation, pigment-specific genes, hormonal signals, enzymatic regulation, and cell-cell exchanges. Occasionally the processes go awry and life-threatening melanomas are generated. Although there has been considerable progress from many laboratories in understanding these processes, much is yet unknown, providing a rich future source of scientific questions yet to be answered.

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